

Oral Assessment in Spanish Literature: A Case Study at the University of Guyana

Evaluación oral en la literatura española: un estudio de caso en la Universidad de Guyana

Avaliação oral na literatura espanhola: um estudo de caso na Universidade da Guiana

Abstract: This study, conducted at the University of Guyana, examined the effectiveness and perceived preference for oral versus written assessments in a Spanish literature course. Data were collected through online questionnaires administered to students and lecturers, structured interviews with lecturers, and an analysis of student performance records. The research aimed to identify which assessment method (oral, written, or a combination) was most effective in enhancing academic achievement and communicative competence. Findings showed that most students preferred oral assessments and supported a blended approach combining oral presentations with written exams. Lecturers likewise favoured oral assessments, considering them more appropriate for evaluating communicative skills. An analysis of mark sheets revealed consistently better student performance in oral assessments across all academic periods reviewed. The study recommends incorporating oral assessments into the curriculum to promote a more dynamic and effective evaluation model for foreign language instruction.

Keywords: Oral assessments, Spanish as a Foreign Language, Spanish literature, University of Guyana.

Resumen: Este estudio, realizado en la Universidad de Guyana, examinó la efectividad y las preferencias percibidas entre la evaluación oral y escrita en un curso de literatura española. Los datos se recopilaban mediante cuestionarios en línea dirigidos a estudiantes y docentes, entrevistas estructuradas con los docentes y un análisis de los registros de desempeño académico. La investigación tuvo como objetivo identificar qué método de evaluación (oral, escrito o una combinación) resultaba más eficaz para mejorar el rendimiento académico y la competencia comunicativa. Los resultados mostraron que la mayoría de los estudiantes prefería las evaluaciones orales y apoyaba un enfoque combinado que integrara presentaciones orales con exámenes escritos. Los docentes también favorecieron la evaluación oral, considerándola más adecuada para

valorar las habilidades comunicativas. El análisis de las planillas de calificaciones reveló un rendimiento estudiantil consistentemente mejor en las evaluaciones orales durante todos los períodos académicos revisados. El estudio recomienda incorporar la evaluación oral al currículo como una estrategia más dinámica y eficaz para la enseñanza de lenguas extranjeras.

Palabras clave: Evaluación oral, español como lengua extranjera, literatura en español, Universidad de Guyana.

Resumo: Este estudo, realizado na Universidade da Guiana, analisou a eficácia e as preferências percebidas entre avaliações orais e escritas em um curso de literatura espanhola. Os dados foram coletados por meio de questionários on-line aplicados a estudantes e professores, entrevistas estruturadas com os docentes e uma análise dos registros de desempenho acadêmico. A pesquisa teve como objetivo identificar qual método de avaliação (oral, escrito ou combinado) se mostrou mais eficaz para melhorar o desempenho acadêmico e a competência comunicativa. Os resultados indicaram que a maioria dos estudantes preferia as avaliações orais e apoiava uma abordagem combinada que integrasse apresentações orais com provas escritas. Os professores também favoreceram a avaliação oral, considerando-a mais apropriada para avaliar as habilidades comunicativas. A análise das planilhas de notas revelou um desempenho estudiantil consistentemente melhor nas avaliações orais em todos os períodos acadêmicos analisados. O estudo recomenda a inclusão da avaliação oral no currículo como uma estratégia mais dinâmica e eficaz para o ensino de línguas estrangeiras.

Palavras-chave: Avaliação oral, ensino de espanhol, literatura espanhola, Universidade da Guiana.

Table of Contents

Introduction	4
Context	4
Justification	5
Literature Review	5
Importance of Spanish Literature in Higher Education	5
Types of Assessment in Higher Education	6
Evaluation of Spanish Literature in Higher Education	8
Purpose of Teaching Spanish Literature to Students of Spanish as a Foreign Language (SFL).	9
Methodology	9
Research Design.....	9
Data Collection Methods and Instruments	9
Population and Sample.....	10
Results	11
Conclusions	14
Appendixes	15
Appendix 1: Lecturer Survey Questionnaire.....	15
Appendix 2: Structured Interview Guide for Lecturers	16
Appendix 3: Student Survey Questionnaire	17
Appendix 4: Analysis of Marksheets	18
References	19

Introduction

The study of Spanish literature at the University of Guyana aims to examine the effectiveness of oral assessments as a means to evaluate students' independent thinking skills. The goal is to provide a comprehensive analysis of the use of oral assessments in the Spanish literature course, considering the challenges and opportunities within this academic context (Herrero et al., 2022).

The study aims to assess the current state of oral assessments in the Spanish literature course at the University of Guyana, identify the strengths and weaknesses of this method, and propose recommendations for its improvement (Manrique et al., 2020). The problematic context of the COVID-19 pandemic led to the emergence of technology as a specific method for assessments, facilitating both lecturers and students in the search for digital assessments. This resulted in a flexible approach in the education system, where oral assessments became more prevalent than written assessments, altering the structure in which these evaluations were developed (Ramos, 2022). From this, the question arises: How do oral assessments improve communication skills in online Spanish literature teaching compared to written assessments?

Context

The study of Spanish literature at the University of Guyana aims to examine the effectiveness of oral assessments as a means to evaluate students' independent thinking skills. The goal is to provide a comprehensive analysis of the use of oral assessments in the Spanish literature course, considering the challenges and opportunities within this academic context. The significance of this in-depth study lies in its potential to contribute to the ongoing dialogue about best practices in literary education (Herrero, 2022).

The study aims to assess the current state of oral assessments in the Spanish literature course at the University of Guyana, identify the strengths and weaknesses of this method, and propose recommendations for its improvement. The problematic context of the COVID-19 pandemic led to the emergence of technology as a specific method for assessments, facilitating both lecturers and students in the search for digital assessments. This resulted in a flexible approach in the education system, where oral assessments became more prevalent than written assessments, altering the structure in which these evaluations were developed (Casanova & Daniel, 2021).

Justification

Research becomes necessary in order to understand the effectiveness of oral assessments in teaching Spanish literature. In the university context, this topic has not been thoroughly addressed, and the research could provide specific contributions to the region in the field of education. Conducting this study will offer a broader perspective on teaching practices and student learning through this assessment mechanism, as well as help improve communication in a foreign language, in this case represented by Spanish (Cañadas, 2020). Furthermore, educators, students, and curriculum developers could consider the study as a contribution to improving teaching and assessment practices in the field of Spanish literature at the university level at the University of Guyana.

Literature Review

Spanish literature at the university level as a foreign language holds significant importance for students, as it allows them to explore cultural and linguistic aspects that are integral to the Spanish-speaking world. As such, incorporating Spanish literature into the university curriculum not only enriches students' understanding of the language and cultural heritage but also contributes to the development of critical thinking and analytical skills (Cambridge Assessment International Education, 2023).

In the educational environment, various assessment methods are employed to measure students' mastery of the discipline. These assessment types range from written exams, research papers, and group projects to oral assessments (Castro, 2020). Defined by their interactive nature, oral assessments also have the potential to foster a dynamic learning environment, allowing students to engage in open dialogue and express their interpretations of literary works in a more nuanced manner (García et al., 2022).

Importance of Spanish Literature in Higher Education

The study of Spanish literature is of significant importance for several reasons. Firstly, it provides students with a deep understanding of the cultural and historical heritage of the Spanish-speaking world. Through the analysis of literary works, students gain insights into the social norms, beliefs, and values that have shaped Spanish culture over the centuries (Martínez, 2023).

Additionally, studying a second language using various assessment mechanisms, particularly oral ones, provides students with the opportunity to reinforce their reasoning and

critical thinking skills in the second language. It allows them to analyse and interpret what they have learned and take advantage of linguistic opportunities to express themselves, thereby strengthening communication and enriching the learning of the second language (Rosales, 2023).

Types of Assessment in Higher Education

In the educational field, there are various types of assessments used to measure student performance. Among the most common are written assessments, oral assessments, and practical assessments. Each type has its own characteristics and is used in different educational contexts (Diaz, 2020). Written assessments typically include multiple-choice tests, essays, or development exercises, while practical assessments involve performing specific tasks or projects. In contrast, oral assessments require students to communicate verbally, either through presentations, debates, or classroom discussions (Olarie & Ruiz, 2022).

Oral assessments have the advantage of allowing a broader and more flexible evaluation of students' learning, focusing on skills related to communication and oral expression, as well as their ability to think critically and argue their viewpoints. Moreover, this type of assessment fosters the development of presentation and public speaking skills, which are valuable in their professional training. However, oral assessments also present challenges, as they can generate anxiety in students and require a higher degree of preparation from lecturers. In summary, oral assessments are a valuable tool in the educational field, allowing the evaluation of communication and critical thinking skills, though they require additional preparation from both lecturers and students (Bazan et al., 2023).

Oral Assessments

Oral assessments play a significant role in the daily practice of flexible education, as they enhance students' understanding and communication in Spanish or any other subject or discipline they are studying (Pirela, 2022). This type of assessment helps students articulate their knowledge and allows them to evaluate their understanding of the topic, whether individually or in groups, through presentations, questioning, or group debates. In other words, this assessment method enables students to critically engage with communication challenges (Varela & Alvarez, 2024).

It is necessary to explain that oral communication in an academic discipline fosters active student participation and helps understand their thoughts and conventional environment.

Additionally, it promotes dialogue and strengthens the curriculum's future development in mastering the discipline (Valdebenito et al., 2023).

Comparison Between Oral and Written Assessments

Oral assessments versus written assessments have provided alternatives and enriched teaching and learning processes. Oral assessments have gained prominence as they have adapted to the design of remote education, which is one of the current trends in the educational field, and during the pandemic, they became a solution for adapting to a more effective learning modality (Sanchez et al., 2023). Oral assessments have become more prominent to reinforce students' communication skills and to provide lecturers with a broader perspective on academic evaluation methods (Sandoval et al., 2022).

On the other hand, written assessments are more traditional, easier to prepare and evaluate, and their analysis and interpretation can be adapted to other settings beyond the actual classroom. Therefore, university lecturers often conduct written assessments and then evaluate them during free periods or in alternative spaces. Written assessments are considered to generate less anxiety in students because they do not face the lecturer waiting for their oral responses; instead, they can respond more flexibly without the pressure of immediate oral feedback (Osorio et al., 2023).

Written assessments allow for the evaluation of grammar and writing, as well as the consideration of sentence structure and writing competencies according to the student's level. However, at the university level, integrated approaches are often considered, combining both modalities as a hybrid method of assessment. This means that sometimes written assessments are conducted, and at other times oral assessments are used, to provide students with dynamic evaluation methods (Ministerio de Educación, 2022).

In European universities, mechanisms for 100% online assessments have been found. These assessments are continuous, personalized, frequently use technology and innovation, and their content is interactive to support both lecturers and students, who are characterized by engaging in remote work or what is also called networking (Universidad Europea, 2020).

The Technological University of Jalisco emphasizes oral and written expressions as a form of assessment assisted through digital transformation. They consider that synchronizing with

educational technology enhances learning and improvement, with assessments providing consistent learning outcomes (Cortes et al., 2022).

According to data from the University of Colorado Boulder Campus, frequent assessments include standardized tests and a mix of written and oral assessments, with technology-enhanced assessments providing an approach to address the individualistic focus required by students (Lorrie, 2006).

At the University of Guyana, various types of assessments are conducted to measure students' performance and knowledge. Common assessments include assignments, field visits, mid-term and final exams, forums, labs, long and short essays, research papers, portfolios, professional practice, presentations, proposals, quizzes, and reports (University of Guyana, 2022).

The University of Guyana mandates that all courses each semester include a summative assessment (University of Guyana, 2020). Each lecturer is responsible for determining the assessment methods used to calculate the final grade of a course, subject to approval by the Department, Faculty, School, or relevant Institute Board and the Academic Board.

Evaluation of Spanish Literature in Higher Education

In the past, both oral and written evaluations were part of the assessment methods for the discipline, with written evaluations being more frequent, as they were traditionally used the most. Using these methods allows students to participate in debates, provide feedback on topics, and practice the language with the instructor, not only focusing on grammar but also on conversation, which will ultimately be more beneficial for the student when they need this knowledge (Romero, 2021).

Starting from the 2020-2021 academic year, the course SPW2201 (Introduction to Spanish Literature) began to be taught online, after having been offered in face-to-face format until the previous academic period. The evaluation in both modalities presents similarities and differences: in both, students are assessed through three midterm exams and a final research paper (University of Guyana, 2020). However, the presentation of the final paper differs: in the face-to-face modality, it was submitted as a printed report, while in the online modality, it is presented orally supplemented with a digital report. Additionally, no final exam is conducted in the online modality (see **Table 1**).

Table 1*Comparative Evaluation of Spanish Literature at the University of Guyana*

Aspect	Face-to-Face Modality	Online Modality
Midterm Exams	3	3
Final Research Paper	Printed Report	Oral Presentation and Digital Report
Final Exam	Yes	No

Note. Author's own work (2024).

Purpose of Teaching Spanish Literature to Students of Spanish as a Foreign Language (SFL)

The general purpose of the Spanish literature discipline is to foster a deeper understanding of both the cultural and historical contexts of Spanish-speaking societies. By engaging with literary texts, students gain insight into various cultural nuances and develop critical thinking skills. This enrichment enhances their ability to communicate more effectively in Spanish, improving their skills for exchanging information during travel, on social media, and boosting their confidence in self-expression (Cañadas, 2020).

Methodology

Research Design

The research on evaluation methods for Spanish literature at the University of Guyana had an explanatory scope according to Ramos (2020). It focused on understanding the differences and perceptions related to these methods. Data were meticulously collected and analysed to determine why certain methods were more effective or preferred. The study went beyond a simple comparison between oral and written assessments; it explored the impact of these methods on learning, participation, and student performance.

By exploring into the attitudes of both students and lecturers, the research aimed to provide clear explanations for educational outcomes, offering insight into specific factors and dynamics within the university's educational context. This quantitative research, according to Calle (2023), focused on gathering numerical data from a significant number of students and lecturers over six academic periods (from 2017-2018 to 2022-2023) to assess the effectiveness of oral and written evaluations in teaching Spanish literature at the University of Guyana.

Data Collection Methods and Instruments

This section outlines the methods and instruments used in this research for data collection (see **Table 2**). Two online questionnaires were utilized through Google Forms to gather information from both lecturers and students regarding their opinions on evaluation methods (see

Appendices 1 and 3). Lecturers were also interviewed via Zoom to obtain more specific information (see **Appendix 2**). Additionally, marksheets were analysed, where the scores for each evaluation and the final grade are recorded (see **Appendix 4**). The results from these four instruments are statistically summarized to uncover patterns and correlations.

Table 2

Data Collection Methods and Instruments for Lecturers and Students

Study Population	Method	Instrument
Lecturers	Survey	Online questionnaire hosted on Google Forms
Lecturers	Structured Interview	Interview guide via Zoom
Students	Survey	Online questionnaire hosted on Google Forms
Students	Performance Analysis	Analysis of marksheets

Note. Author’s own work (2024).

Population and Sample

All 17 students enrolled in the SPW2201 course at the University of Guyana from 2017-2018 to 2022-2023 were invited to participate in the survey via email. They were provided with the data collection instruments through a Google Forms link. Of the students contacted, 16 responded, resulting in a 94.12% participation rate from the total student population.

The study also included the two lecturers who taught the SPW2201 course during the same six academic periods. Both lecturers were sent separate Google Forms questionnaires via email, and both completed the forms, representing 100% of the teaching staff involved in the course during the study period. This ensured that the views of all lecturers who had taught the course were captured, providing a comprehensive perspective on assessment methods in the course.

The following tables summarize the sample of students (**Table 3**) and lecturers (**Table 4**) who participated in this study:

Table 3

Students Sample

Academic Year Interval	Study Program	Number of Students
2017-2018 to 2019-2020	Bachelor of Arts (Spanish)	1
	Bachelor of Education (Secondary)	6
2020-2021 to 2022-2023	Bachelor of Arts (Spanish)	2
	Bachelor of Education (Secondary)	7
Total of Students		16

Note. Author’s own work (2024).

Table 4
Lecturers Sample

Years of Experience	Academic Rank	Years Taught These Courses	Number of Lecturers
15 years	Lecturer I	2017-2018, 2018-2019, 2020-2021 (shared)	1
10 years	Lecturer II	2019-2020, 2020-2021 (shared), 2021-2022, 2022-2023	1
Total of Lecturers			2

Note. Author’s own work (2024).

The selected student sample adequately reflects the students’ experiences and perceptions regarding the evaluation methods. On the other hand, including all the lecturers who taught these courses during the study period ensures a comprehensive view of the evaluation practices and their impact on the teaching and learning of Spanish literature at the University of Guyana.

Results

This study was based on surveys and analysis of grade records to assess the effectiveness of oral versus written assessments in the SPW2201 course at the University of Guyana. The data obtained from questionnaires administered to students and faculty reveal significant trends regarding perceptions and academic outcomes associated with both assessment methods.

Ultimately, after applying all assessment instruments, a detailed analysis of the obtained grades was conducted. It was found that out of the maximum grade of 5, an average of 4.5 was achieved, indicating a notable improvement in the grades obtained in the Spanish literature discipline, resulting in a standard deviation of 1.03. This statistical value means that while there is some variation in the data, it is not extremely high, meaning that the grades obtained are relatively close to the mean. This allows for the interpretation that when comparing data sets, the higher grades prevail, indicating more variability around the mean measure (see **Table 5**).

Table 5
Averages and Standard Deviations of Student Perceptions Regarding the Utility of Studying Spanish Literature

Evaluated Aspect	Average	Standard Deviation
Utility of studying Spanish literature	4.5	1.03
Development of communicative competence	4.6	1.06

Note. Author’s own work (2024).

In terms of preference for evaluation methods, 44% of the students indicated that they were “Strongly agree” that oral assessments are preferable to written ones, 31% were “Agree”, 19% were “Neutral”, and only 6% were “Disagree” (see **Figure 1**). When asked about the convenience of combining written exams and oral presentations, 44% of the students were “Strongly agree”, 31% were “Agree”, 13% were “Disagree”, 6% were “Strongly disagree”, and 6% were “Neutral” (see **Figure 2**).

Figure 1

Students’ Preferences for Evaluation Methods (Oral vs. Written Assessments)

Note. Author’s own work (2024).

Figure 2

Students’ Preferences for Combining Written Exams and Oral Presentations

Note. Author’s own work (2024).

The lecturers also expressed a preference for oral assessments, considering them more suitable for evaluating students’ communicative competence. All respondents (100%) agreed that oral assessments better promoted this competence compared to written assessments.

Since the student groups spanned various academic years, we considered the period from 2017-2018 to 2019-2020, which was before the COVID-19 pandemic when classes were fully in-person and assessments were predominantly written. During the pandemic (2020-2021), classes transitioned entirely online, significantly altering lecturer-student interactions and assessment methods. After the pandemic, from 2021-2022 to 2022-2023, classes continued exclusively online. This setup allowed the research to compare assessment results across these different formats.

The analysis of the marksheets reveals performance trends across assessment types. Specifically, 78% of students across all six academic periods (2017-2018 to 2022-2023) performed better in written assessments. However, 85% of students achieved higher grades in oral assessments (see **Figure 3**).

Figure 3

Comparison of Final Grade Averages by Assessment Type (Oral vs. Written)

Note. Author's own work (2024).

The study suggests that oral assessments are more effective than written assessments for improving the communicative competence of SFL students in the SPW2201 course at the University of Guyana. This finding aligns with previous studies highlighting the effectiveness of oral assessments in developing communicative skills in language teaching. Oral assessments allow students to practice speaking and listening comprehension in a more direct and realistic manner, which is crucial for the development of communicative competence.

Lecturers support this positive view of oral assessment methodology, considering that it can offer significant benefits in teaching Spanish literature. Through this methodology, students demonstrate theoretical knowledge and apply their skills in real communicative contexts, which is

crucial for effective language use in various situations. Oral assessments also promote greater student participation and engagement, as they require coherent ideas and provide immediate feedback, which is valuable for learning and development.

On the other hand, written assessments focus on grammatical accuracy and students' ability to record and reproduce information, which is not sufficient for the complete development of communicative competence. Combining oral and written assessments can provide a more holistic and balanced approach, evaluating both grammatical precision and theoretical knowledge, as well as students' ability to apply this knowledge in real communicative situations.

Conclusions

The study reveals that students at the University of Guyana are developing their communicative competence more effectively through oral assessments rather than written ones. This approach is favoured by both students and lecturers as it enhances academic performance and promotes more active and participatory learning. Implementing oral assessments could significantly improve students' communicative competence, which is crucial for their success in learning SFL. Combining oral and written assessments could provide a more comprehensive and balanced evaluation of student performance, allowing them to demonstrate both theoretical knowledge and their ability to use the language in real-life situations.

Professional training in oral assessment techniques is recommended to ensure the effective and fair application of this method. This could include strategies for designing and evaluating oral presentations and techniques for providing constructive feedback. Further studies should be conducted to explore the impact of oral assessments in other educational courses and to identify best practices for their implementation. Future research could explore how different assessment methods affect learning in various contexts and disciplines, providing a more comprehensive understanding of effective educational assessment practices.

Appendixes

Appendix 1: Lecturer Survey Questionnaire

Instructions: Dear lecturer, we appreciate your participation in this survey, which aims to gather information about the evaluation methods used in the SPW2201 course at the University of Guyana. Please check the box that best represents your level of agreement for each row. Kindly answer the following questions honestly.

Demographic Questions:

- Full Name: _____
- Years of experience as a lecturer at the University of Guyana: _____
- Academic Rank (Lecturer I, Lecturer II, Senior Lecturer, etc.): _____

Survey Questions:

N°	Questions	Totally Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Totally Agree
1	The study of Spanish literature is important for SFL (Spanish as a Foreign Language) students.					
2	The study of Spanish literature contributes to the development of communicative competence and linguistic skills for SFL students.					
3	For face-to-face evaluation of Spanish literature, oral assessments are more convenient than written assessments.					
4	For face-to-face evaluation of Spanish literature, it is preferable to combine oral and written assessments.					
5	For online evaluation of Spanish literature, oral assessments are more convenient than written assessments.					
6	For online evaluation of Spanish literature, it is preferable to combine oral and written assessments.					

Note. Author's own work (2024).

Appendix 2: Structured Interview Guide for Lecturers

Instructions: Dear lecturer, we appreciate your participation in this interview aimed at gathering detailed information about the evaluation process in the SPW2201 course at the University of Guyana. Your responses will be treated confidentially and will significantly contribute to our research. We sincerely thank you for your time and collaboration.

Demographic Questions:

- Full Name: _____
- Years of experience as a lecturer at the University of Guyana: _____
- Academic Rank (Lecturer I, Lecturer II, Senior Lecturer, etc.): _____

Interview Questions:

1. In which academic years did you lecture the SPW2201 course starting from 2017-2018?
 - a. 2017-2018
 - b. 2018-2019
 - c. 2019-2020
 - d. 2020-2021
 - e. 2021-2022
 - f. 2022-2023
2. Why do you consider it important for SFL (Spanish as a Foreign Language) students to study Spanish literature?
 - a. It improves students' communicative competence.
 - b. It enhances the four language skills of students.
 - c. It provides a deeper understanding of Hispanic culture.
 - d. Other (please specify)
3. What do you think is the best way to evaluate Spanish literature in in-person classes?
 - a. Three written exams
 - b. Three oral presentations
 - c. A written research paper
 - d. A written research paper combined with an oral presentation
 - e. A final written exam
 - f. Other (please specify)
4. What do you think is the best way to evaluate Spanish literature in online classes?
 - a. Three written exams
 - b. Three oral presentations
 - c. A written research paper
 - d. A written research paper combined with an oral presentation
 - e. A final written exam
 - f. Other (please specify)

Note. Author's own work (2024).

Appendix 3: Student Survey Questionnaire

Instructions: Dear student, please answer the following questions based on your experience with the evaluation in the SPW2201 course. Check the box that best represents your level of agreement for each row. Your participation will remain anonymous, and your honest responses will help improve the evaluation methods used in these courses.

Demographic Questions:

- Full Name: _____
- Academic Year you took the SPW2201 course: _____
- Program you are (or were) enrolled in at the University of Guyana: _____
- Current Year of Study at the University of Guyana (if applicable): _____

Survey Questions:

N°	Questions	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	The study of Spanish literature as an SFL student was beneficial.					
2	The study of Spanish literature contributed to the development of my communicative competence and language skills.					
3	Oral evaluation (oral presentations) is preferable to written evaluation (written exams) in Spanish literature.					
4	A combination of written exams and oral presentations is more convenient for evaluating Spanish literature.					

Note. Author's own work (2024).

Appendix 4: Analysis of Marksheets

Student N°	Academic Year	Final Grade
Student 1		
Student 2		
Student 3		
Student 4		
Student 5		
Student n		

Note. Author's own work (2024).

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